

EXPLORING (EMERGING) MYCOTOXINS RISK IN BEANS: A GLOBAL ALLIANCE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE RESILIENCE

D2.2 – Report on toxicity profiling and combinatory toxicity

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DELIVERABLE TITLE	Report on toxicity profiling and combinatory toxicity
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D2.2 reports on the implementation and initial execution of the toxicity profiling activities carried out within Task 2.1 (M6–M24) of the MYCOBEANS project. Task 2.1 aims to establish an integrated *in silico*–*in vitro* framework to assess cumulative toxicity associated with legume-based food products under realistic exposure scenarios. Occurrence and co-occurrence data generated in WP1 revealed complex and previously underexplored co-exposure patterns in legume-based foods, requiring dedicated prioritisation before experimental testing.

A tiered strategy combining *in silico* prioritisation with advanced *in vitro* models has been implemented to guide the selection of compounds and mixtures for toxicity profiling, with particular emphasis on emerging mycotoxin-driven co-exposure scenarios. Computational screening supports hypothesis generation and experimental prioritisation, which are addressed through functional testing in intestinal barrier models and extended to hepatic and immune cellular systems to capture metabolism-related, genotoxic, immunomodulatory and endocrine-related responses. A multi-endpoint approach has been established to integrate complementary readouts and to support the identification of biologically relevant response patterns.

During the reporting period, activities focused on the development, optimisation and harmonisation of the integrated workflow across WP2 partners, as well as on the initiation of experimental testing following occurrence-driven prioritisation. Quantitative consolidation of combinatory toxicity data is currently ongoing and will be addressed in the subsequent project phase. Resulting scientific outputs will be disseminated through peer-reviewed publications and open-access repositories in line with Open Science principles.

1. Purpose and scope of the activities

Deliverable D2.2 documents the implementation and initial execution of the toxicity profiling framework developed within Task 2.1 (M6–M24). The overarching objective of Task 2.1 is to establish *an integrated testing platform* for the systematic assessment of toxicity associated with food-relevant contaminants and bioactive constituents occurring in bean-derived products, with particular emphasis on combined exposure scenarios.

The approach is designed to capture both the effects of individual compounds and the biological responses arising from their combined presence under realistic co-occurrence conditions. The toxicological scope encompasses regulated and emerging mycotoxins, co-occurring phytotoxins, bioactive polyphenols such as isoflavones, and process-related contaminants including Maillard reaction products. Compound and mixture selection implemented in this deliverable is based on the prioritisation framework and contaminant list defined in Deliverable D2.1, ensuring alignment with product-relevant occurrence data generated within WP1.

Within this context, Deliverable D2.2 focuses on the establishment and operationalisation of the integrated *in silico–in vitro* workflow, the initiation of toxicity profiling activities across selected cellular models, and the definition of experimental layouts and endpoints. Quantitative consolidation of toxicity outcomes will be addressed in subsequent deliverables, in alignment with the planned progression of WP2 activities.

In parallel, Task 2.2 addresses bioaccessibility, bioavailability and interactions of contaminants and bioactive constituents with the gastrointestinal environment. As a consequence, the interpretation of toxicity profiling outcomes generated within Task 2.1 is closely linked to observations emerging from Task 2.2, particularly with respect to modulation of compound release during digestion and potential colonic biotransformation. This functional interconnection reflects the need to integrate hazard-related and exposure-related information when addressing cumulative toxicity under realistic food-related conditions.

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Figure 1. Conceptual workflow of Task 2.1.

2. Input from WP1 and rationale for prioritisation

The prioritisation strategy adopted in Task 2.1 is grounded on occurrence and co-occurrence data generated within WP1 through market-level screening of legume-based products collected in Italy and Thailand. A total of 132 samples, including raw legumes, flours and pasta, and processed snacks, were analysed for a broad spectrum of regulated and emerging mycotoxins as well as plant-derived toxins. This activity provided a comprehensive overview of contamination patterns under realistic market conditions. Such prioritisation process was further informed by close interaction with industrial partners involved in the MYCOBEANS consortium, ensuring that selected contaminants, matrices and exposure scenarios reflect realistic production chains and commercially relevant legume-based food products.

Overall, approximately half of the analysed samples were positive for at least one toxin, with a high frequency of multi-toxin co-occurrence, particularly in processed products. Legume-based snacks emerged as the most critical category, showing both the highest prevalence of contamination and the most complex toxin profiles. Across all product categories, contamination scenarios were dominated by the co-occurrence of multiple mycotoxins, often involving combinations of regulated and non-regulated compounds, confirming that realistic exposure cannot be adequately addressed through single-compound approaches.

A key outcome of WP1 was the prominent role of emerging mycotoxins, which represented the most prevalent toxin class across matrices and countries. In particular, *Alternaria* toxins (including i.e. alternariol, alternariol monomethyl ether and tenuazonic acid) were frequently detected, often in co-occurrence with other fungal metabolites such as beauvericin, enniatins and fusaric acid. These compounds contributed substantially to the overall contamination burden, especially in processed products, and were identified as recurrent drivers of multi-toxin exposure scenarios. While the toxicological profiles of regulated mycotoxins are relatively well characterised and provide a reference framework, toxicological data for many emerging mycotoxins are still limited, in some cases even at the single-compound level. As a consequence, the assessment of combined

effects involving these substances represents an additional layer of complexity, which needs to be addressed through dedicated and integrated experimental approaches.

Although different contamination patterns were observed between Italian and Thai samples, co-occurrence of multiple emerging mycotoxins was a consistent feature across both sample sets, reinforcing their relevance for cumulative toxicity assessment.

In this context, compound and mixture selection within Task 2.1 was aimed at deepening representative exposure patterns reflecting real-world consumption. Prioritisation therefore integrates frequency of occurrence, co-occurrence patterns, toxicological relevance and structural diversity of contaminants, with particular emphasis on *Alternaria* toxins and other emerging mycotoxins as key contributors to combined exposure.

This approach explicitly recognises cumulative toxicity as a central scientific challenge and provides a robust rationale for advancing selected compounds and mixtures - especially *Alternaria*-driven scenarios - to *in vitro* toxicity profiling within WP2.

2.1 Definition of priority co-exposure scenarios

Occurrence and co-occurrence data generated in WP1 showed contamination patterns characterised by high chemical complexity. In legume-based products, exposure scenarios differed from those typically reported for cereal-based matrices, which represent the main reference for regulated mycotoxins. As a result, the relevant co-exposure scenarios were not fully defined at the beginning of the project and required specific prioritisation before experimental testing.

Across samples, contamination was consistently dominated by emerging mycotoxins. Alternariol (AOH), alternariol monomethyl ether (AME) and tenuazonic acid (TEN) were frequently detected and often co-occurred. These compounds were commonly found together with emerging ionophoric mycotoxins, including beauvericin (BEA) and enniatins (ENNs), and with fusaric acid.

This group of compounds defines the most recurrent co-exposure scenario identified in WP1 and represents the main focus of Task 2.1.

Regulated mycotoxins such as fumonisins (FUM) and deoxynivalenol (DON) were detected with variable frequency and are included as reference compounds to allow comparison. Ochratoxin A and aflatoxins were only sporadically detected and are therefore considered episodic contaminants rather than systematic contributors to cumulative exposure in legume-based foods. Also given their well-known toxicological profile, OTA and AFs were not prioritised in the activities.

Given the number of possible combinations arising from these patterns, a limited number of co-exposure scenarios was selected based on frequency of occurrence and biological plausibility. Priority was given to combinations involving the *Alternaria* toxin cluster (AOH, AME, TEN) and ionophoric mycotoxins (BEA, ENNs) also considering combination with DON or FUM, as these mixtures represent the most relevant and recurrent exposure conditions identified in WP1.

2.2 Biological rationale: intestinal interface and immunomodulation

The co-occurrence patterns identified in WP1 required an approach focused on functional effects rather than on single-compound toxicity. The working assumption underlying Task 2.1 is that the selected co-exposure scenarios may affect biological systems through functional modulation, particularly at concentrations relevant for food exposure.

The intestinal epithelium is addressed as the primary biological interface for these scenarios. It represents the first site of contact for foodborne contaminants and integrates barrier function, transport processes and stress-responsive signalling. Moderate alterations of barrier integrity or transport capacity may influence uptake and downstream responses without causing extensive cell damage. For this reason, perturbation of intestinal barrier function is investigated as a potential early event in cumulative toxicity.

Immunomodulation is investigated as a related downstream response. Several of the prioritised mycotoxins are known to interact with signalling pathways involved in inflammation and cellular stress. Under co-exposure conditions, these interactions may result in non-additive modulation of immune-related pathways. NF- κ B-dependent responses are therefore used as functional indicators of pathway modulation under sub-cytotoxic conditions.

Endocrine-related and genotoxic endpoints are included as additional dimensions of toxicity. Their evaluation is integrated within a multi-endpoint framework to identify complementary aspects of biological response under realistic co-exposure conditions.

2.3 Integrated *in silico*–*in vitro* pipeline

To address the complexity of the selected co-exposure scenarios, Task 2.1 has been implemented through a structured pipeline integrating *in silico* analyses and *in vitro* testing. The pipeline is used to support experimental prioritisation and data interpretation, and to reduce chemical complexity while preserving biological relevance.

In silico approaches are therefore applied as a decision-support tool throughout Task 2.1. They are used not only to support experimental prioritisation, but also to investigate plausible mechanisms of action and to identify molecular initiating events relevant for the observed biological responses. In particular, *in silico* analyses are applied to explore interactions between prioritised compounds and biological targets or interfaces relevant for the selected endpoints, including membrane interactions and signalling pathways related to intestinal function, immunomodulation, endocrine activity and DNA damage response.

In this framework, *in silico* and *in vitro* activities are closely integrated and inform each other in an iterative manner, rather than being applied as consecutive steps in a linear pipeline. *In silico* outputs support the selection of compound combinations and concentration ranges, and contribute to the interpretation of experimental results by providing mechanistic context for functional responses observed *in vitro*.

The first experimental level focuses on functional assessment at the intestinal interface. Barrier integrity is evaluated by transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER). Uptake and transport are assessed using transwell systems. Cell viability is measured in parallel using the sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay to exclude non-specific cytotoxic effects. This level allows the identification of co-exposure scenarios inducing functional alterations under sub-cytotoxic conditions.

Selected scenarios are then assessed for modulation of biological pathways. Immunomodulatory responses are evaluated using an NF- κ B reporter assay and cytokine expression analysis in intestinal cells under inflammatory stimulation. Estrogen receptor-mediated activity is assessed using an ER-dependent luciferase assay. Oxidative and antioxidative activity is measured using the DCF-DA assay to contextualise pathway responses.

Genotoxicity and mutagenicity are addressed at a subsequent level. Mutagenic potential is evaluated using the bacterial reverse mutation (Ames) test. DNA damage response signalling is assessed by in-cell Western analysis of γ H2AX. Given the potential for signalling interference, γ H2AX responses are interpreted in combination with *in silico* analyses targeting kinases involved

in the DNA damage response. Discordant responses across endpoints are considered informative for identifying functional modulation.

A limited number of prioritised co-exposure scenarios is further investigated using transcriptomic and metabolomic analyses. These approaches are applied in a targeted manner to support mechanistic interpretation and identify consistent biological responses.

Overall, this pipeline reflects an adaptive strategy developed in response to the unexpected complexity of co-occurrence patterns observed in legume-based foods. Experimental testing within Task 2.1 was initiated after prioritisation of realistic exposure scenarios, in order to avoid arbitrary testing and to ensure biological relevance of the generated data.

3. Role of *in silico* prioritisation

Within Task 2.1, *in silico* approaches are used to support the mechanistic understanding of toxicity associated with prioritised food-related contaminants and bioactive constituents. Their role extends beyond experimental prioritisation and focuses on molecular-level interactions and potential molecular initiating events underlying observed biological responses.

In silico analyses are applied to compounds selected on the basis of WP1 occurrence and co-occurrence data. Molecular structures are characterised in three dimensions, accounting for stereochemistry as well as metabolic and/or process-related modifications relevant for molecular interactions. This enables comparative analyses among structurally related compounds and supports interpretation of differences in biological activity.

Molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations are applied using validated protocols to investigate interactions between prioritised compounds and selected biological targets or interfaces relevant for WP2 endpoints, including intestinal, immune, endocrine and DNA damage-related pathways. Where relevant, free-energy-based calculations are used to refine comparisons among closely related compounds or isomeric forms.

4. Tiered *in silico*–*in vitro* workflow for intestinal barrier assessment

Within Task 2.1, activities related to intestinal barrier assessment were coordinated at UNIVIE to develop and implement a shared experimental workflow across WP2 partners, including UNIPR, QUB, TU and NSTDA. The workflow was designed to enable functional evaluation of intestinal barrier responses under realistic exposure conditions and to ensure harmonisation of experimental approaches among partners.

Experimental assessment of intestinal barrier function was conducted using established epithelial models, including Caco-2 and HT-29 monocultures and a mucus-producing Caco-2/HT29-MTX-E12 co-culture system. These models were selected to capture complementary aspects of epithelial organisation, barrier integrity and transport processes. Functional assessment was performed using transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements, complemented by uptake and transport studies in transwell systems.

Cell viability was assessed in parallel to functional endpoints to exclude non-specific cytotoxic effects and to ensure that observed barrier alterations occurred under sub-cytotoxic conditions. This approach allowed the identification of exposure scenarios inducing functional modulation of the intestinal barrier rather than general cell damage.

The established workflow was applied initially in single-compound testing to validate assay performance and define biologically relevant concentration ranges for prioritised contaminants, with particular emphasis on *Alternaria* toxins. These activities provided the experimental basis for the ongoing transition towards combinatory testing aligned with the co-occurrence patterns identified in WP1.

Implementation of the intestinal barrier workflow was supported by secondment activities among WP2 partners. Secondments facilitated hands-on training, exchange of expertise and harmonisation of experimental procedures, contributing to a shared understanding of both computational and experimental components of Task 2.1.

At M24, the intestinal barrier platforms are fully implemented and actively used within WP2. Functional outputs generated from these models are used to inform subsequent testing in complementary cellular systems and to support prioritisation of co-exposure scenarios for further investigation.

5. Extension to systemic models (hepatic and immune)

While the intestinal epithelium represents the primary interface for dietary exposure, selected activities within Task 2.1 extend toxicity assessment to systemic cellular models relevant for xenobiotic processing and immune response. This extension was implemented to capture biological effects that may not be evident at the intestinal level alone.

Hepatic models were established to address metabolism-related and DNA damage-related endpoints. HepG2-based assays are used to assess cell viability and DNA damage response signalling under exposure conditions prioritised in the intestinal workflow. These models provide complementary information on cellular stress and hazard-related endpoints relevant for downstream interpretation.

Immune-related responses are assessed using THP-1-based cellular systems. These models are applied to evaluate modulation of immune signalling pathways, with a focus on NF- κ B-dependent responses. The use of immune cell models allows the investigation of pathway-level effects that may arise following intestinal exposure and uptake.

At M24, both hepatic and immune in vitro platforms are established and actively used within WP2. Their application is guided by the outcomes of the intestinal barrier assessment, ensuring that systemic testing is focused on prioritised exposure scenarios. Integration of intestinal, hepatic and immune models supports a coherent evaluation of cumulative toxicity across biological compartments and contributes to the alignment of functional responses observed under co-exposure conditions.

6. Toxicological endpoints and readouts

Task 2.1 adopts a multi-endpoint strategy to understand complementary dimensions of toxicity under realistic co-exposure scenarios. Endpoints are selected and applied within an integrated framework, with the aim of supporting biologically meaningful interpretation rather than relying on single readouts.

General cytotoxicity is assessed using the sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay across cellular models. This endpoint is applied to define sub-cytotoxic concentration ranges and to exclude non-specific effects that could confound functional interpretation.

Functional endpoints related to intestinal barrier integrity and transport are assessed using transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements and uptake studies in transwell systems. These endpoints provide information on epithelial organisation and permeability under exposure conditions prioritised within Task 2.1.

Immunomodulatory responses are evaluated using complementary approaches. NF- κ B-dependent reporter assays are applied to assess modulation of immune-related signalling pathways. In addition, inflammatory responses in intestinal epithelial cells are evaluated under IL-1 β stimulation through quantitative PCR analysis of selected cytokines (TNF α , IL-6, IL-8). This approach allows the assessment of epithelial inflammatory responses in a controlled pro-inflammatory context.

Endocrine-related activity is assessed using estrogen receptor-dependent luciferase assays, providing information on potential modulation of hormone-responsive pathways under single-compound and co-exposure conditions.

Genotoxicity and mutagenicity are addressed using complementary endpoints. Mutagenic potential is evaluated using the bacterial reverse mutation (Ames) test. DNA damage response signalling is assessed by in-cell Western analysis of γ H2AX. Given the possibility of pathway-level

modulation, DNA damage–related endpoints are interpreted in combination with other functional readouts and *in silico* analyses supporting data interpretation.

Oxidative and antioxidative activity is monitored using the DCF-DA assay to contextualise functional and pathway-related responses and to support discrimination between redox-mediated and non-redox-mediated effects.

At M24, these endpoints have been applied primarily in single-compound testing to validate assay performance and define biologically relevant experimental conditions. As combinatory testing progresses, convergent or discordant responses across independent endpoints are used to prioritise exposure scenarios for further investigation.

Within this framework, secondees were trained not only in the technical execution of cellular and molecular assays, but also in the integrated interpretation of endpoint responses across models and readouts. The work focused on the critical evaluation of functional, pathway-based and hazard-related endpoints in relation to exposure scenarios and mechanistic hypotheses.

7. Outlook and next steps

The activities carried out within Task 2.1 have led to the implementation of a structured and integrated framework for *the assessment of cumulative toxicity under realistic food-related exposure scenarios*. At M24, the core components of the *in silico–in vitro* pipeline are established and operational, and experimental testing of selected mixtures has been initiated following the prioritisation of relevant co-exposure scenarios.

The initial phase of Task 2.1 required a dedicated effort to characterise contamination patterns in legume-based foods and to define biologically meaningful toxin combinations. This step was necessary due to the unexpected complexity of co-occurrence profiles identified in WP1, which differed from those commonly described for regulated cereal-based commodities. Experimental

testing was therefore initiated after exposure scenarios and decision criteria were sufficiently defined to ensure biological relevance.

In the forthcoming phase, activities within Task 2.1 will focus on the systematic application of the established pipeline to selected co-exposure scenarios. This includes the progression from single-compound testing to combinatory testing aligned with WP1 co-occurrence patterns, and the integration of functional outputs across intestinal, hepatic and immune models.

Targeted uptake and transport studies in transwell systems will support the interpretation of functional effects observed at the intestinal level. Selected co-exposure scenarios showing consistent or informative response patterns will be further investigated using transcriptomic and metabolomic analyses to consolidate mechanistic interpretation.

Figure 2. Advanced follow-up investigations for selected compounds and mixtures.

The outputs generated within Task 2.1 will inform subsequent activities within WP2, including product-related bioaccessibility assessment addressed in Deliverable D2.3, and will provide a scientific basis for downstream mitigation strategies developed in WP3. Overall, this phased approach ensures continuity between exposure-driven prioritisation, functional toxicity profiling and mechanistic consolidation under realistic food-related conditions.

8. Secondments integration

The implementation of Task 2.1 was supported by secondment activities among WP2 partners, aimed at facilitating knowledge exchange and hands-on training on integrated in vitro and in silico toxicological approaches. These activities contributed to the harmonisation of experimental workflows and analytical strategies across participating institutions.

Outgoing secondments from QUB to UNIVIE supported activities related to advanced cellular models and functional toxicity assessment. Incoming secondments from TU/BIOTEC to UNIVIE contributed to the experimental implementation and optimisation of the integrated Task 2.1 workflow. In parallel, secondments involving UNIPR supported training and exchange of expertise on computational modelling and in silico approaches applied within WP2.

The in silico component of Task 2.1 also represented a relevant training element within the MSCA Staff Exchanges framework. Computational activities required the integration of chemical, biological and toxicological knowledge, going beyond the routine application of software-based workflows. Trainees were trained to interpret molecular modelling outputs in relation to biological function and experimental data, including target selection, evaluation of molecular interactions and formulation of mechanistic hypotheses, in close interaction with experimental activities.

Overall, secondment activities enabled bidirectional transfer of expertise and supported the coordinated development and application of the WP2 toxicity assessment framework, while

contributing to the development of interdisciplinary skills aligned with the objectives of the MSCA programme.

9. Scientific outputs and open science dissemination

Activities carried out within Task 2.1 are generating scientific outputs, including integrated experimental datasets and mechanistically informed evaluations of cumulative toxicity under realistic co-exposure scenarios. At M24, these outputs are under analysis and consolidation.

Dissemination of results is planned through peer-reviewed publications and scientific presentations in accordance with the project timeline. In line with Open Science principles and MSCA requirements, datasets supporting published/disseminated results will be made available through open-access repositories, ensuring transparency, reproducibility and reuse by the scientific community and relevant stakeholders.